

Project¹ Number: 101086293

Project Acronym: CRISPIt

Project title: Bridging fundamental knowledge and novel technology
to increase rice heat tolerance

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Contact Person: **Sílvia Coimbra** (scoimbra@fc.up.pt)

 0000-0001-9421-2538

Universidade do Porto, Faculdade de Ciências

Created by: **Ana Marta Pereira** (ambacpereira@fc.up.pt)

Universidade do Porto, Faculdade de Ciências

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¹ The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

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1. Data Summary

This document constitutes the first version of the Data Management Plan for the CRISPRit project (Deliverable 4.1). It specifies Data Governance and handling of data in the project, what types of data are expected to be generated along the project, if and how it will be made open and accessible for verification and re-use. It will also specify how it will be curated and preserved, with details such as ethical, privacy and security issues. This document follows the template provided by the European Commission in the Participant Portal and will benefit from the expertise of BioData.pt, an association specialized in biological data analysis and management.

The data used and generated along CRISPRit will be mainly **transcriptomic data and genetic tools and constructs**. These data will come from two different plant species: *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Oryza sativa*, under control and heat stress conditions, grown in controlled conditions. These data will be the foundation of the whole project, being essential to achieve all the proposed objectives: 1) define heat stress features and marker genes in Nagina22 rice variety, 2) generate a new transcriptomic dataset 3) obtain and fully characterize mutants from the chosen genes to deliver rice heat stress lines produced by CRISPR technology. Most of the transcriptomic data generated will be concerned with Work Package 1 (WP1) and will allow the selection of the genes to be studied in the following WPs. Genetic tools and constructs will be mainly derived from WP2, allowing to understand these gene's functions and relatedness to heat stress tolerance.

CRISPRit will generate new data and will also re-use already existing data. The re-used data will be already published data in public repositories. RNA-seq data of control and heat-treated reproductive tissues during anthesis carried out using Nagina22 (N22 *Oryza sativa* variety) will be used and is already published by González-Schain et al., 2016².

File size can range between 10Kb and 1Tb.

To support the management life cycle for all data that will be collected, processed or generated by the action, the **acquired data (results)** will be evaluated by the Coordinator of CRISPRit and after evaluation, she will give a recommendation to each WP leading beneficiary, which will ultimately decide the target of each particular dataset. If decision of dissemination stands, different dissemination channels will be considered depending on whether the dataset comes in form of a scientific publication or in contrast, is a large dataset, as for example a transcriptomics results.

² González-Schain et al., 2016. Plant Cell Physiol 57(1), 57-68.

2. FAIR data

2. 1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Transcriptomic data will be generated via RNA-Seq using high-throughput sequencing platforms. The resulting raw data (fastq files) and the alignment information (BAM files) will be stored in the European Nucleotide Archive³ (ENA) which accepts sequence reads and associated analyses. Data submitted to ENA is automatically exchanged between International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration⁴ (INSDC) partners: NCBI and DDBJ. These data bases make data publicly available to the community allowing for new discoveries by comparing these raw data sets with others. Secondly, analysed data files will be deposited in the EBI Array Express Archive of Functional Genomics Data⁵. This ensures that transcriptome experiments are available for reuse and combined analyses. Both, the EBI and the NCBI curates' data that is deposit to their archives, which ensure uniformity of the transcriptome data and its cognate experiments.

Regarding **genetic tools and constructs** that become available during the completion of CRISPic, plasmids and useful genetic constructs that are released from IPR protection will be deposited at the Addgene non-profit public repository⁶. Genetic sequences will be available to any requesting laboratory. Addgene develops a strong interaction between participating laboratories to implement data curation and standardization of the samples that are stored in their DNA bank.

The **minimum information standard** (Minimum Information for Biological and Biomedical Investigations⁷), a set of guidelines for reporting data derived by relevant methods in biosciences, will be used, along with Metadata Standards Catalog⁸. This ensures that the data can be easily verified, analysed, and clearly interpreted by the wider scientific community. I will also facilitate the foundation of structured databases, public repositories, and development of data analysis tools. Individual minimum information standards are brought by the communities of cross-disciplinary specialists focused on issues of the specific method used in experimental biology.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

The data for the CRISPic project will be produced by various researchers from the participating laboratories using general guidelines and procedures to standardize the operative procedure of data and help to decide which data is dedicated to dissemination and which data requires IPR protection.

³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

⁴ <https://www.insdc.org/>

⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress>

⁶ <https://www.addgene.org/>

⁷ <https://fairsharing.org/MIBBI>

⁸ <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

The metadata will be open on the **Research Data Repository of the University of Porto**. Data resulting from the research will be available upon request after project publications.

Along the project a protected area is being developed at the CRISPIt website (<https://www.fc.up.pt/crispit/>), accessible to all PIs and lab members by entering a dedicated password at a LOGIN link. After entering the protected area, different folders will be found:

CRISPIt_Management_Dissemination folder is reserved to the Coordinator, i.e. the coordinator can add and remove files whereas all the other partners can only see them, and different information are stored in independent subfolders.

The sub-folder Coordination/Dissemination - contains information and data discussed during the Internal Meetings, i.e. programs of the meetings, list of participants with signatures, reports of the meetings and .pdf files of all the presentations. In addition, information related to the main dissemination events are also stored there.

The sub-folder Deliverables - contains data and information related to all the different deliverables. It will include excel files with lists of candidate genes, sequence data for genes and proteins, plasmids, relevant protocols, etc.

The sub-folder CRISPIt_Official_Documents – contains the Grant Agreement, the Consortium Agreement and the .pdf file of the proposal.

The sub-folder Report – contains the programs and/or reports of the Zoom meetings together with the different Reports of the Review Meetings.

In addition to that, a folder for each partner is created. Here, each of the PIs can add and remove files in its own folder. Information and data related to Deliverables, Dissemination events and Reports will be store in there. The coordinator is also allowed to add and download files in each of the partner folders.

At the CRISPIt protected area, a link to the **Research Data Repository of the University of Porto** and **OpenAIRE** is also available. This is an open-source web application to share, preserve, cite, explore, and analyse research data. This Data Repository will host the CRISPIt virtual Archive with long term preservation guarantee. The virtual Archive is accessible to all partners of CRISPIt project through the link available at the protected area. Furthermore, data and information related to Deliverables classified as “Public” are made available to everybody.

2.3. Making data interoperable

The data generated and used along CRISPIt will follow the standard formats for each type of data, compatible with open software applications, as much as possible. All the formats for sequence annotation, for example, or RNA-seq results used will be stored at public repositories as described in section 2.1 and the specified formats are already used by all the scientific community. Metadata will be openly avai-

lable. Metadata will be available in a form that can be harvested and indexed (managed by the used repository / repositories).

standardized vocabularies will be used for all data types to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability, as referred in section 2.1 (Minimum Information for Biological and Biomedical Investigations & Metadata Standards Catalog).

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

We will be working with the philosophy as open as possible for our data. The data cannot become completely open immediately because of:

- 1) patent-related business reasons;
- 2) we want to publish the papers first.

Data that is not legally restrained will be released after a fixed time period (Five years), unconditionally. We have a consortium agreement that arranges Intellectual Property.

All the information that may be shared openly will be made available through public repositories as described in section 2.2.

As an assurance of data quality we will be using the following quality processes along experiments:

- calibrating measurements;
- repeat samples/measurements;
- standardized data capture/recording;
- Data Entry validation;
- data peer review;
- controlled vocabularies;
- measuring samples with known outcome (to monitor consistency).

3. Allocation of resources

Each member of the **CRISPit consortium**, during its course, will be responsible for their own research records while the principal investigator/supervisor has the ultimate responsibility for the laboratory's records. The coordinator will be responsible for data management regarding the whole consortium. To execute the DMP, additional specialist expertise is required, and we have such trained support staff available. We do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in our institutes. Details on persons' responsibilities at this time can be found below.

Ana Marta Pereira and Inês Chaves are responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

Sílvia Coimbra and Nelson Saibo are responsible for reviewing, enhancing, cleaning, or standardizing metadata and the associated data submitted for storage, use and maintenance within a data centre or repository.

Luís Gustavo Pereira and Ana Marta Pereira are responsible for finding, gathering, and collecting data.

Ana Marta Pereira, Inês Chaves, Sílvia Coimbra, Nelson Saibo and Luís Gustavo Pereira are responsible for maintaining the finished resource.

Sílvia Coimbra and Inês Chaves are responsible for the management and proficiency of data including data processing, data policies, data guidelines, and data availability.

4. Data security

All the data that may be used or generated along the project will be stored not only in public and/or private repositories (see section 2.2) but will also be stored in personal and shared computers, on-line storage systems, and back-up storage devices. All publications resulting from the project will be published in **Open Access**.

Record keeping – Lab Notebooks

- Updated and well-organized Lab books will be kept, either written or electronic Lab books.
- Records should be legible, clear, timely, thorough, complete, secure, backed-up, and well-organized. All entries should be in English.
- All Lab books are always available to the supervisors and persons involved in the project using cloud services.
- All notebooks and data are owned by the Labs, but may be copied (without personal identifiers) at the discretion of the supervisor.

Electronic Data Storage and Accession

- All electronic files and data generated (plasmid sequences, excel tables, electronic Lab books, photographs, gels, etc) will be kept on each lab common server, hard disks or clouds at all stages of the research process.
- Data will be recorded in ways that cannot be altered. Records will be protected from destruction (ranging from fading caused by sunlight or flooding to computer crashes) by storing it in different places.
- All original electronic data as well as the modified electronic files will be stored at all times.
- More than one copy of the data will be kept stored in different approved places. Whatever medium is chosen, it is important to make sure that the medium is reliable and that files can still be read at a later date.
- A record of data locations will be maintained.
- To maximize accessibility and long-term value data will be stored in open formats.
- All relevant metadata will be clearly defined and tightly integrated with data.

Biological data storage

- All biological data generated will be appropriately stored for the time recommended after the project is finished.
- All plasmids will be kept in glycerol stocks at -80°C.

- Harvested seeds will be processed promptly (including threshing, cleaning, drying and packaging) and then placed into storage.
- All seeds, wild-type and mutated ones will be stored safely protected from light and in dry conditions.

The possible impact to the project or organization if information is lost is small. The risk of information leak in the project or organization is acceptably low. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is vandalised is small. We are not using any personal information. Only project members will have read access; only selected project members will be able to write data.

5. Ethical aspects

So far, there are no ethical or legal issues regarding the CRISPIt data sharing. If any arises along the project, it will be properly discussed between the coordinators and the leading beneficiaries.

6. Contributors

Sílvia Coimbra

scoimbra@fc.up.pt, 0000-0001-9421-2538

Affiliation: Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade do Porto

Nelson Saibo

saibo@itqb.unl.pt, 0000-0002-6679-3811

Affiliation: universidade Nova de Lisboa

Ana Marta Pereira

ambacpereira@fc.up.pt, 0000-0003-3665-7592

Affiliation: Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade do Porto

Inês Chaves

ichaves@itqb.unl.pt, 0000-0001-7569-3495

Affiliation: Universidade Nova de Lisboa

Luís Gustavo Pereira

lcpereir@fc.up.pt, 0000-0002-8567-3452

Affiliation: Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade do Porto

7. History of changes

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	30.06.2023	▪ Initial version